

Vulnerability Analysis of Trivium FPGA Implementations

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Abstract—Today, the large amount of information exchanged among various devices as well as the growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) demand the development of devices that ensure secure communications, preventing malicious agents from tapping sensitive data. Indeed, information security is one of the key challenges to address within the IoT field. Due to the strong resource constraints in some IoT applications, cryptographic algorithms affording lightweight implementations have been proposed. They constitute the so-called lightweight cryptography. A prominent example is the Trivium stream cipher, one of the finalists of the eSTREAM project. Although cryptographic algorithms are certainly simpler, one of their most critical vulnerability sources in terms of hardware implementations is side channel attacks. In this paper, it is studied the vulnerability of field-programmable gate array (FPGA) implementations of Trivium stream ciphers against fault attacks. The design and implementation of a system that alters the clock signal and checks the outcome is also described. A comparison between real and simulated fault injections is carried out in order to examine their veracity. The vulnerability of different versions of the Trivium cipher and their routing dependences has been tested in two different FPGA families. The results show that all versions of the Trivium cipher are vulnerable to fault attacks, although some versions are more vulnerable than others.

Index Terms—Fault attack, field-programmable gate array (FPGA) implementation, stream cipher, Trivium, vulnerability analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE amount of information daily exchanged in communication networks is growing in an exponential way. A substantial percentage of this information is sensitive. It must therefore be protected in order to preclude malicious use. Cryptography provides techniques, mechanisms, and tools for confidentiality, authentication, integrity, and nonrepudiation. It has been applied for data exchange across large systems. However, nowadays, there are an increasing number of devices with scarce resources and low power (L.P.) consumption, e.g., those suitable for the Internet of Things (IoT). In [1] and [2], Mahmoud *et al.* and Xu *et al.* pointed out the importance and challenges related to security in the IoT,

showing the relevance of secure implementations under strong constraints of power consumption and area, among other aspects. Indeed, the number of lightweight cryptography implementations has significantly increased in recent years. In this context, the use of stream ciphers is one of the best options because of their limited impact on the available resources. However, the behavior of a device must be first comprehensively studied and tested against different attacks in order to know its security level.

The development of encryption algorithms and the increasing length of cipher keys have made attacks over algorithms themselves (either on their weaknesses or by brute force) useless. However, side channel attacks are proving to be highly effective. These attacks obtain the key used by a cryptographic algorithm through attacks over the circuit implementation, either through measurements of physical parameters (power consumption, electromagnetic radiation, and time used by encryption or decryption) or by injecting faults in the circuit through alterations of the operating conditions.

There are different flavors of side channel attacks. Some attacks measure the power consumption during circuit operation and compare it with an estimated consumption. These are the so-called side channel analysis, such as differential power analysis or correlation power analysis, where the attacker uses a model of the power consumption of the underlying circuitry. Assuming a hypothetical power consumption for a key, or for a portion of a key, the attacker compares the power consumption experimentally measured with the consumption provided by the model. Highly correlated measurements would correspond to the same key. Other attacks alter the operating conditions of the hardware until a fault occurs. These are the so-called active fault analysis attacks, such as differential fault analysis (DFA) or differential fault intensity analysis. These attacks compare the output of a circuit with and without faults. If the attacker is able to generate faults in a particular way, it is possible to retrieve the secret key and therefore endanger the security.

A. Previous Works

A number of works analyzing the robustness of the Trivium stream cipher against DFA have been reported in the literature. In [3]–[5], a theoretical attack was carried out. Faults were injected on the cipher internal state in order to retrieve secret information from the device. They showed that if an attacker is able to inject only one faulty bit in the internal state, the security of the cipher could be endangered. These works presented successful attacks using DFA and fault models

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but none of them proved the attack feasibility over physical implementations. They are described in detail in Section II of this paper, which also explains the number of injections needed to retrieve the key using DFA.

B. Our Contribution

Two previous works have presented preliminary results of fault injection over field-programmable gate array (FPGA)-based Trivium implementations. One of them is [6]. It reported a version of the fault injection system applied to the standard Trivium stream cipher implemented in a Spartan III Xilinx FPGA. This paper showed the vulnerabilities of this FPGA-based cipher against fault injections through variations of the clock signal. The second work [7] presented a comparison between experimental results obtained after applying the fault injection system and results obtained after the timing analysis using static and post-route simulations. It also analyzed the relation between faulty bit positions of the internal state and signal delays at the inputs of flip-flops using the timing analysis. A reasonable assumption would be that the bit positions with greatest delays should be the first ones to fail. However, the results showed that the positions that first failed did not correspond to the ones with the greatest delay in the timing analysis.

The aim of this paper is to study the vulnerability of different Trivium designs implemented in an FPGA to fault attacks. This is done by applying a previously reported fault injection system to the different designs. In particular, the vulnerability of four Trivium designs implemented in two different FPGA families against the same attacks is studied. In the case of the Spartan 6 FPGA family, the previous fault injection system design was modified taking into account the technology constraints and the differences between both FPGA families. The tested designs are the standard Trivium, the serial load with internal counter Trivium, the serial load with external counter Trivium, and a L.P. Trivium. An analysis that provides the maximum operating frequencies of these ciphers on FPGAs, thus defining the frequencies needed to inject faults in internal states, is presented. This analysis also allows us to draw general conclusions about the vulnerabilities of these ciphers against fault attack by the alteration of the clock signal. A comparison between experimental results and those obtained in fault injection simulations is also presented. The internal state, sampled many cycles after a fault was injected in the Trivium implemented in the FPGA, is compared with the simulation results of the internal state after having applied the same fault injection at the same clock cycle. This comparison allows us to ensure that the data experimentally measured are correct.

C. Paper Organization

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the state-of-the-art of active fault analysis, reviews the different theoretical fault injection threats applicable to the Trivium cipher, and describes the existing practical techniques for fault injection. Section III introduces the architecture of various Trivium stream cipher designs and describes

the characteristics of the FPGA-based implementation for these ciphers. Section IV presents the structure and design considerations of a fault injection system tailored for fault injections in FPGAs. Section V presents the results obtained. The simulation tests performed to check the accuracy of the experimental tests and the results obtained for each cipher when the proposed fault injection system is applied are considered separately. Finally, conclusions about this paper are drawn in Section VI.

II. ACTIVE FAULT ANALYSIS

Many works focused on an active fault analysis have been reported in the literature, since it was proposed by Boneh *et al.* [8]. In this paper, the authors proposed a theoretical model to break cryptographic circuits based on random fault injections on hardware implementations. They proved that some encryption algorithms are vulnerable against fault injection attacks. Anderson and Kuhn [9] presented a review of low-cost attacks based on the fault analysis for different cryptographic systems [Rivest–Shamir–Adelman (RSA), data encryption standard (DES), and other block ciphers] as well as for smart cards. By applying DFA, they retrieved the key of the DES cipher by using between one and ten ciphertexts. These works showed the fault attack effectiveness over cryptographic systems through the study of faulty system outputs. In [10], Biham and Shamir proposed the so-called differential cryptanalysis of the data encryption standard. A differential analysis method was presented as a general theoretical method to study different cryptographic systems, including private key cryptosystems. In [11], Biham and Shamir combine fault analysis and differential cryptanalysis. Using a fault model and some cryptanalytic techniques, they are able to retrieve the secret keys of different cryptographic devices theoretically resistant to tampering. Particularly, they achieve to obtain the secret key of a DES cryptographic system from an average between 50 and 200 ciphertexts, proving that the security of cryptographic systems can be endangered by the combination of a fault model and differential analysis.

After these first works, many others have been reported within this field. Various cryptographic algorithms have been considered, including symmetric key systems, such as block ciphers and stream ciphers. As an example, some general techniques to attack the ciphers RC4, LILI-128, and SOBERt-32 are presented in [12]. When it comes to the DFA over block ciphers, [13] and [14] showed that AES is vulnerable to fault analysis. In [13], the attack is implemented in a personal computer, whereas in [14], it is performed in an experimental mode over smart cards. There have been studies about lightweight block ciphers, such as PRESENT [15] or [16] where it is theoretically demonstrated that injecting faults in intermediate states or in round keys is possible to retrieve the secret key. DFA has been implemented over stream ciphers too, in particular over the ciphers Mickey, Grain, and Trivium. These ciphers are the finalists of the eSTREAM project for hardware implementations. In [17] and [18], linear equations are proposed in order to, after perform fault insertions in the Mickey stream cipher, enabling access to the internal state and thus break the system. Concerning the Grain stream cipher,

Fig. 1. Clock glitch and fault injection representation.

a theoretical analysis is presented in [19] in order to determine linear equations that allow to restore the cipher internal state. In [20], the theoretical model is enhanced, proposing a realistic number of fault injections without restrictions about their timing and location. They achieve breaking the system in a few minutes. Finally, for the Trivium stream cipher, a number of attacks are presented in [3]–[5], [12], and [21]–[23] in a theoretical way. They prove that if it is possible to inject only one faulty bit in the internal state then it is possible to break the system.

This paper focuses on analyzing the vulnerability of the Trivium stream cipher implemented in the FPGA against DFA. Next, it is briefly summarized the previous works on this topic. In [3], Hojsik and Rudolf study the Trivium vulnerability against DFA attacks. They conclude that in order to retrieve the cipher key and the initialization vector (IV), it is necessary to inject only one fault in a random position of the cipher internal state and repeat this attack over the same key and an IV. This attack would be effective over an average of 43 fault injections on the internal state. The same authors presented an improvement of this attack [4] where they were able to reduce the number of fault injections to an average of 3.2 to retrieve the key and the IV. On the basis of this paper, the cryptographic analysis is enhanced in [5], retrieving the key and the IV over an average of 3.7 fault injections. Other analyses have been presented afterward. In [21], the average number of fault injections is reduced to 2. In [22], various improvements are reported concerning attack restrictions. Finally, the fault injection average to retrieve the key and the IV is further reduced to 1 in [23].

From the point of view of the attacker, the common feature shared at a fundamental level by all of the DFA works related to the Trivium cipher is the need of injecting only one fault in the internal state. In other words, an attacker must be able to change only one bit of the internal state in order to retrieve the key and the IV. Thus, if an attacker is able to insert one faulty bit, the security of the cipher system where the Trivium is implemented will be endangered. However, none of these previous works experimentally test these attacks over a Trivium hardware implementation. They do not therefore show whether implementations of the Trivium cipher are vulnerable against this kind of attack.

In [24], various methods that can be used to induce faults in CMOS circuits are reported. Examples of attacks based on the exploitation of faults as well as on a series of countermeasures to thwart these attacks are described. They distinguish two kinds of circuit faults: provisional (transient) and destructive (permanent). Provisional faults have reversible effects, and the circuit will recover its original behavior after the system is reset or when the fault stimulus ceases. Conversely, destructive faults are created by introducing defects on the chip structure on purpose, and they have a permanent effect that will affect the behavior of the chip permanently.

Concerning mechanisms for fault injections over cryptographic circuit implementations, many alternatives have been proposed in the literature. In [25] and [26], a review of fault injection techniques and countermeasures to avoid circuit faults is presented. Among the various fault injection techniques, those based on modifying the voltage supply, reducing it (underpowering [27]), or inducing pikes (power pikes [28]) have proven their effectiveness. Other effective attacks are based on the alteration of temperature conditions [29], the effect of electromagnetic radiation over the circuitry (electromagnetic disturbances [30]), or the application of a laser beam [31].

Another effective mechanism to cause a circuit fault is altering the clock signal. This technique consists in reducing the time between the active edges of the clock signal until a wrong system operation takes place. This technique was used to carry out an experimental differential attack in the work presented by Street and Lafayette [9]. This attack was applied over different devices, such as RSA and DES. The same technique is used in [32] in order to attack different block ciphers belonging to ISO/IEC 18033-3, such as AES and DES. Experimental results are reported. In [33], Agoyan and Dutertre studied this technique upon a theoretical analysis based on practical experiments, explaining why these faults occur and when they could appear. Finally, this technique is also applied in [34] to perform an attack over an AES cipher implemented on an FPGA.

Fig. 1 shows a diagram of how the clock signal can be altered in order to produce a fault. This is a low-cost technique whose practical realization depends on the maximum operation frequency of the particular cryptographic device. For

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the Trivium stream cipher.

devices operating at low frequencies, it can be easily applied. For devices such as Trivium ciphers, which can work at high frequencies, its applicability gets more tricky. In any case, this is the technique used to inject faults over the Trivium cipher, and it has proved to be very effective.

III. TRIVIUM STREAM CIPHER

The Trivium stream cipher [35] is one of the eSTREAM project finalists. It is a synchronous cipher designed to generate up to 2^{64} bits of key stream from an 80-bit secret key and an 80-bit IV. The cipher architecture is based on three shift registers comprising 288 bits in total, as well as combinational logic to provide feedback. Just like other synchronous stream ciphers, the underlying algorithm needs to be initialized with the load of 288 bits into the shift register (internal state) comprising one secret key, one IV, and a stream of zeros and ones. Before generating a valid key stream, the cipher needs to run for 1152 clock cycles. From that moment on, it generates a valid pseudorandom bit sequence.

The 288 bits of the internal state are distributed along three shift registers with different lengths. The first shift register has 93 bits, the second is made up of 83 bits, and the third comprises 111 bits. The feedback for each shift register is generated with AND and XOR operations. The key stream is the result of XOR operations on some bits in the shift register. Fig. 2 shows the schematic of the Trivium internal structure.

In this paper, the vulnerability of Trivium against fault injections on FPGA implementations is analyzed. It has been tested the *standard* version of Trivium, where the load of the key and the IV is done in both parallel mode and serial mode. In addition, some tests have been carried out on a L. P. version of Trivium. This L.P. implementation of Trivium was presented in [36] and further explored in [37].¹ The analysis of the results obtained for these implementations will allow us to generalize whether Trivium cipher implementations are vulnerable to DFA attacks. Sections III-A and III-B describe the main distinctive features of these implementations.

A. Standard Implementation

The standard implementation of Trivium loads the key and the IV values in parallel mode. This implementation requires,

¹Area, power, and timing results from different Trivium implementations are presented and discussed in [37].

Fig. 3. Schematic detail of the *standard* Trivium implementation.

including a multiplexer at the input of each of the 288 flip-flops making up the internal state. This multiplexer selects between the input data in loading mode and the previous flip-flop in operating mode. Fig. 3 shows a detail of the schematic of this implementation. Note the multiplexer between each flip-flop. In FPGAs, these multiplexers are implemented with lookup tables that increment the delay between flip-flops.

Two extra versions of this cipher have been implemented in order to test the behavior of Trivium without multiplexers between flip-flops encoding internal state. In this case, the load of the key and the IV is done in serial mode. The multiplexers are not needed in these implementations, since the data in load mode come from the previous flip-flop. The first serial version of the Trivium, serial with internal counter (S.I.C.), has an internal circuit to control the load of the 288 bits encoding the internal state. This internal circuit consists of a 9-bit counter (from 0 to 287) and a simple state machine. The second serial version of the Trivium, serial with external counter (S.E.C.), does not have any internal control circuit. The count of the 288 bits associated with the serial load has to be performed externally.

B. Low-Power Implementation

This implementation includes a power reduction technique consisting in parallelizing the shift register in [36] and [37]. The key concept applied in this technique is the division of the shift register into two halves. During the shift register operation, data coming in even cycles are stored in one of the halves, whereas data coming in odd cycles are stored in the other half. One of the registers is called the even register, whereas the other is called the odd register. As a result, the clock triggering the even and odd registers has a frequency, which is half the input frequency. Note that from an external point of view, the shift register operates upon the original single frequency. Power reduction is achieved, because only half of the data are shifted during each clock cycle. Thus, each portion of data has to go through half of the flip-flops to reach the output. The introduction of this technique in Trivium achieves a remarkable reduction of power consumption. On the other hand, it also demands the introduction of small modifications in its implementation consisting mainly in adding combinational circuits to the feedback paths. Fig. 4 shows a schematic representation of this L.P. implementation of Trivium.

IV. SYSTEM DESIGNED FOR FAULT INJECTION

In order to test the vulnerability of Trivium against fault analysis attacks, the FPGA system has been designed and implemented to inject faults in Trivium ciphers by altering the

TABLE I
MAXIMUM OPERATING FREQUENCIES FOR EACH CIPHER

Trivium	Spartan 3E				Spartan 6			
	Standard	S.I.C. ¹	S.E.C. ²	L.P. ³	Standard	S.I.C. ¹	S.E.C. ²	L.P. ³
Max. Freq. (MHz)	316.66	300	325	80	550	500	580	80

¹ Trivium — Serial with Internal Counter.
² Trivium — Serial with External Counter.
³ Trivium — Low Power.

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of L.P. Trivium.

clock signal. The maximum operating frequency of Triviums must be taken into account for the design of such a system. All the required tests to ensure that the detected errors correspond to cipher malfunctioning rather than wrong data sampling have been carried out. This section describes the main features of the designed system.

A. Clock Frequencies for Trivium in FPGA

FPGAs use special lines for the propagation of global signals, e.g., clock signals, in order to reduce their skew. These global signals enable high operating frequencies for sequential systems with low combinational logic implemented in the FPGA. As Trivium cipher implementations (and in general all stream ciphers) consist of shift registers with some feedback paths, their implementations on FPGA technologies are able to reach very high frequencies. The maximum operation frequency is therefore the main parameter of Trivium to be taken into account when designing the fault injection system. Note that this fault injection system must generate a signal with a frequency slightly higher than the maximum operating frequency, which is different for each version of the implemented Trivium.

It has been analyzed the vulnerability of four versions of Trivium in two Xilinx FPGA devices, namely the Spartan

3E XC3S500E and the Spartan 6 XC6LX16. In order to find out the maximum frequency of each version of Trivium per device, the digital clock manager (DCM) of the corresponding FPGA device has been used. In the case of the Spartan 6, the system was modified taking into account the technology constraints. In this case, two DCMs have been used in order to generate the short pulse due to the specific characteristics of this FPGA family and ciphers. The DCM allows to create output clocks featuring lower and higher frequencies than the input frequency from an input clock with a prescribed frequency. The determination of the maximum frequency dismisses the load cycles associated with the key and the IV, because no fault injection is performed in those cycles. The resulting maximum operating frequencies for each cipher per device are shown in Table I.

Note that, apart from the L.P. Trivium whose maximum frequency is lower due to its particular clock structure, the maximum operating frequencies of the Trivium implementations are very high. For the Spartan 3E XC3S500E device, the maximum operating frequency is 311 MHz. The Trivium with parallel load stops working properly at 316 MHz, whereas the S.E.C. version is the fastest one, reaching 325 MHz. For the Spartan 6 device, the results are similar. The maximum frequency of the device is 400 MHz. The Trivium implementation based on parallel load fails at 550 MHz, whereas the S.E.C. version keeps being the fastest one, reaching 580 MHz. These results mean that the system to be developed for injecting failures in the ciphers should be able to generating shorter pulses than the minimum guaranteed for the device. Problems arise if the pulses are too short: they can be filtered out by the device. The system to be developed must therefore generate pulses with a frequency very close to the failure frequency.

The generation of pulses at higher frequency than the maximum frequency of the device creates further difficulties in the system to be developed. Such difficulties arise not only when it comes to creating and transmitting signals with this frequency, but also because it is necessary to be sure that the whole system is working properly and it is only the Trivium cipher the block having failures in its operation. Furthermore, our interest is not only to inject faults in the operation of Trivium ciphers, but to introduce a single fault in the internal register. It must be, therefore, found an optimal frequency, which depends on the version of Trivium and the device itself. This frequency must fulfill two basic conditions: 1) it must be high enough to inject only one faulty bit in the internal state and 2) it should not be so high as to be filtered out by the device.

B. Structure of the Designed System

The designed system is able to inject faults in the Trivium cipher as well as to detect the number and position of the faults injected. The aforementioned fault injection is carried out by designing a circuit that alters the clock signal, as shown in Fig. 1. It is able to control the clock cycle where the short pulse is generated. In order to detect the faults injected in the ciphers, three copies of the same version of the Trivium have been implemented in the device. In the first cipher, the clock signal is not altered. It constitutes the so-called *golden Trivium* featuring correct operation. In the other two versions, the system introduces a short pulse, at the programmed clock cycle, in the clock signal. By comparing the behavior of the *golden Trivium* with the other two versions, it is possible to know whether a fault has been injected. The design of these Triviums has been modified to have access to their internal state in order to enable the analysis of the number of faults as well as their positions.

The generation of short pulses in the clock signal has been done by switching between two clock signals. One of them features low frequency (*clk_low*), suitable for the correct operating of the ciphers. Conversely, the second one features high frequency (*clk_fast*), slightly higher than the maximum operating frequency of the implemented ciphers. In order to generate a short pulse, the system controls the cycle at which the switching takes place. Both clocks have been generated using a DCM available in the FPGAs. The DCM can generate clocks with lower and higher frequencies than that of the input clock. In order to select one of the two clock signals, a special clock multiplexer available in the FPGA was used. This multiplexer allows the selection between two clock signals without injecting any glitch. It is crucial ensuring that only one short pulse is injected. In case more than one short pulse is generated, the fault injection would be wrong and could give rise to more than one fault.

A state machine underpins the whole system for fault injection. It initializes the Trivium (loading the key and the IV), controls the specific cycle at which the pulse is generated, samples the internal state of the three copies of the Trivium, and compares those internal states. The comparison is performed in serial mode.

The state machine offers some other features for the sake of generalizing the results. In addition to the load of different keys and IVs randomly generated, it is possible to choose the clock cycle where the pulse is inserted. It is also possible to select the clock cycle where the internal states are sampled. These options enable to test how the injected faults relate to different keys, IVs, and clock cycles.

Although it is not possible to know the effect of a short pulse injection in the clock signal by simulation, the control of the clock cycle at which the internal state is sampled allows to verify whether the detected faults are correct. To this end, in simulations, it is modified the internal state in the same way as it is detected in the FPGA device. The internal state is then sampled a number of cycles later. Fault injection is similarly performed on the device, but the internal state is now sampled after the same number of cycles as the simulation.

The comparison between both internal states ensures that the detected faults correspond to the actual faults introduced in the cipher.

V. RESULTS

The whole mechanism for the clock signal pulse generation and Trivium ciphers has been designed in VHDL and implemented in two FPGA devices, namely a Spartan 3E XCS500E and a Spartan 6 XC6LX16. Data sampling has been done with the ChipScope Pro Analyzer. As explained earlier, previous theoretical works state that injecting only one faulty bit in the internal state suffices to endanger the security of the ciphers. Taking this into account, it will be considered that an effective or satisfactory fault injection occurs when only one bit is changed. Those cases where the number of altered bits is higher than one are considered ineffective attacks. It should be remembered that, as far as we know, the works previously presented do not describe experimental fault injections against stream ciphers, and it is not therefore possible to compare these results or techniques with previous outcomes.

A. Checking the Correctness of the Measurements

Since both pulse generation into the clock signal and data sampling take place in the FPGA, it is not possible to control the signal delays so accurately as with a logic analyzer. This demands extra tests, also needed to ensure a correct sampling of the internal state of the Trivium ciphers and to check that the resulting data correspond to the actual value of that internal state.

These tests consist in introducing the same faults that have been detected in the experimental tests in the functional simulation. The Trivium internal states acquired experimentally and by simulation are compared two thousand clock cycles after the fault injection took place. If both internal states are equal at that time instant, then they were also equal two thousand cycles before, which means that the experimental measurement of the inserted fault is correctly done.

Fig. 5 shows a comparison between the results experimentally obtained when a fault is injected, and the results that would be obtained by a functional simulation when the same fault is introduced. Each graph shows, in serial mode, a section of the content of the internal state of the Trivium without and with fault injection (*Correct State and Incorrect State*). The top graphs depict the internal state at the clock cycle just after the short pulse generation in the clock line occurs. The bottom graphs show the internal states two thousand clock cycles after the same pulse generation. The two graphs on the left represent experimental data, whereas the graphs on the right represent simulation data. Note that only one fault is injected for the graphs in Fig. 5. It has been verified that after two thousand clock cycles, the internal state without fault injection is totally different to the internal state with fault injection. Moreover, the values of the internal states experimentally obtained when a fault is injected are the same as those obtained by simulation. These results verify the successful injection of a fault and its correct measurement.

Fig. 5. Comparison between correct and faulty internal states—both experimental and from simulation. (a) In the injection clock cycle. (b) 2000 clock cycles after the injection.

TABLE II
NUMBER OF FAULTS INJECTED FOR EACH KEY/IV PAIR AND INSERTION CYCLE

Trivium	Insertion cycle	Spartan 3E				Spartan 6			
		Pair A	Pair B	Pair C	Pair D	Pair A	Pair B	Pair C	Pair D
Standard	1200	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
	1300	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
	1500	2	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
	1750	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
S.I.C.	1200	1	2	0	1	1	1	1	1
	1300	1	1	1	2	0	1	1	1
	1500	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0
	1750	1	0	2	2	1	1	1	1
S.E.C.	1200	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2
	1300	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1
	1500	1	1	0	1	2	1	0	2
	1750	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0

B. Results for Standard Trivium

Due to its particular internal structure, the results of the attacks applied on the L.P. version of Trivium will be presented separately in Section V-C. Now the results obtained for the standard, S.I.C. and S.E.C. versions of Trivium are presented.

The results reported next encompass the analysis of the number of faults injected in the cipher under test, the behavior of the ciphers implemented in parallel mode against the same attack, and the capacity and efficiency of the system to inject faults. Concerning the analysis of the number of injected faults, the objective is to find out how many faults were injected for each case and study whether the system is able to inject only one faulty bit in the internal state. Regarding the behavior of the ciphers, the goal is to know how the same attack affects the two faulty copies of the cipher under test when they are compared with the faulty-free cipher implemented. Finally, with respect to the third scope of results, the aim is knowing the system capacity to inject faults in the ciphers and its efficiency on this task. In other words, we want to determine whether the system is able to inject only one faulty bit in the internal state or, on the contrary, it injects more than one. Among all pairs of secret keys and IVs randomly set, the results for four key-IV pairs used in two families of Xilinx FPGAs are presented.

TABLE III
FAULT INJECTIONS ON CIPHERS IN PARALLEL IMPLEMENTATIONS

Trivium	Insertion cycle	Spartan 3E		Spartan 6	
		T1	T2	T1	T2
Standard	1200	1	0	0	1
	1300	2	1	1	0
	1500	2-3	2	0	0
	1750	1	1	1	0
S.I.C.	1200	1	1	0	1
	1300	0	1	1	0
	1500	1	1	1	1
	1750	0	1	0	1
S.E.C.	1200	0	1	0	1
	1300	0	1	1	2
	1500	1	1	1	2
	1750	1	1	2	1

Table II shows the number of faults injected in the internal state of the standard, S.I.C. and S.E.C. versions of Trivium. The insertion cycle refers to the clock cycle where the pulse in the clock line is induced. The different pairs *A*, *B*, *C*, and *D* denote tests performed with different pairs of key-IV. When the number of faults is one, an effective fault inject took place,

TABLE IV
CAPACITY AND EFFICIENCY INJECTION OF THE SYSTEM IN SPARTAN 3E AND SPARTAN 6

Trivium	Spartan 3E		Spartan 6	
	Injection Capacity	Injection Efficiency	Injection Capacity	Injection Efficiency
Standard	59%	91%	38,44%	100%
S.I.C.	63,75%	68%	41%	92,99%
S.E.C.	56,44%	74,97%	59,56%	85,52%

i.e., for these conditions, only wrong bit was injected in the internal state. When the number of faults is zero, no fault was injected. Finally, a number of faults greater than one means ineffective injection, as only one faulty bit is required.

According to Table II, it has been possible to inject only one faulty bit in the internal state for all the versions of Trivium per pair key/IV. Although for some clock cycles it was not possible to inject any faults, there is always a clock cycle for each Trivium per pair key/IV where it is possible to inject one fault. Furthermore, even though the results differ when the same test is performed over different FPGAs, it is always possible to inject an effective fault.

The relation between fault injections and routing in the FPGA has also been analyzed. For this purpose, the fault injection system has been applied to two identical ciphers implemented in the FPGA operating on the same inputs. The results for the same clock pulse injection over two Trivium ciphers ($T1$ and $T2$) working with the same inputs are summarized in Table III. Note that the behavior of both ciphers implemented in parallel against the same attack and under the same conditions is slightly different. Still, it is possible to inject effective faults in both cases. The results shown in Tables II and III prove not only the vulnerability of FPGA implementations of Trivium ciphers against attacks by fault insertion through alteration of the clock signal, but also that this vulnerability persists for different pairs of key/IV, different families of FPGAs, and different realizations on the same device.

It has also been analyzed the positions where the fault is injected in the internal states. The results show that the positions where the fault tends to appear are those of the bits that are used by the cipher for feedback or logic operations. Bits close to these ones are also fault prone. Furthermore, it has been observed that the fault position changes depending on the clock cycle at which the short pulse is induced in the clock line. The results for the first case in Table II—pair A for the three implementations of Trivium—show that no fault injection was achieved for clock cycle 1200. However, for clock cycle 1300, the fault injection is done in bit position 3, for clock cycle 1500 in bit positions 3 and 2, and for clock cycle 1750 in bit position 2. Applying the same conditions in Spartan 6, the outcome changes. For clock cycle 1200, the faulty bit position is 0, while for clock cycle 1750, the faulty bit is 51. No fault injection was accomplished for the other two cases. It can be concluded that the ciphers behave slightly differently against the same attack for different insertion cycles, regardless of an implementation on the same FPGA family or on a different one. In the other tests, the faulty

bit positions are normally positions 1, 2, 3, 51, 93, 94, 96, 151, 178, 179, and 195. As previously mentioned, most of them are either those bits used by the cipher for feedback or logic operations or bits near these ones.

Finally, the capacity and efficiency for fault injection of the designed system have been analyzed. The injection capacity is the percentage of occurrences where the system was able to inject faults in the ciphers. Both successful and unsuccessful injections are considered for the calculation of this percentage.

The injection efficiency is the percentage of occurrences, considering all of the injections, where the fault injections are effective or successful, i.e., they give rise to only one faulty bit. In order to obtain both parameters, each test has been repeated 100 times for the same cipher implementation, clock insertion, and key/IV pair—that is, around 9600 tests have been performed.

The results are summarized in Table IV. They show that the injection capacity of the designed system is high (always over 38%) and the injection efficiency for effective fault injections is even higher. In these tests, the efficiency is always over 68%, reaching 100% for the standard Trivium with parallel load. This means that for the designed system, the number of injections needed to retrieve the key through DFA would be minimal due to the fact that the injection of only one wrong bit in the internal states is ensured.

C. Results for Low-Power Trivium

For the L.P. Trivium, the same tests and the same analysis as for the standard Trivium are applied. Table V shows the number of faults injected for four key/IV pairs, four insertion cycles, and two devices of two Xilinx families. It can be seen that for each implementation, and for each pair of key/IV, it is always possible to introduce a single fault in the internal register. It is not achieved in all cycles where faults are injected, but there are always some cycles where it is achieved. Just like the previous cases, the results change slightly when the implementation is performed in the Spartan 3E or in the Spartan 6.

Regarding the routing dependence, Table VI summarizes the results of attacks over two Triviums implemented in parallel in the same FPGA. Only in two cases, the results are not equal. Note that the fault positions are not always the same in both ciphers. The positions that tend to fail are those of the flip-flops used by the cipher for its operation.

Finally, Table VII shows the system capacity and efficiency for fault injection in this Trivium implementation. As in the previous cases, each test has been repeated

TABLE V
NUMBER OF FAULTS INJECTED FOR EACH KEY/IV PAIR AND INSERTION CYCLE IN THE L.P. TRIVIUM

Insertion cycle	Spartan 3E				Spartan 6			
	Pair A	Pair B	Pair C	Pair D	Pair A	Pair B	Pair C	Pair D
1200	1	1	1	1	1	3	1	1
1300	0	1	1	1	2	1	2	2
1500	1	1	1	2	1	0	1	3
1750	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1

TABLE VI
FAULT INJECTIONS ON CIPHERS IN PARALLEL IMPLEMENTATIONS

Insertion cycle	Spartan 3E		Spartan 6	
	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2
1200	1	1	1	2
1300	1	2	2	2
1500	1	1	1	1
1750	1	1	1	1

TABLE VII
CAPACITY AND EFFICIENCY INJECTION OF THE SYSTEM IN L.P. TRIVIUM

FPGA	Injection Capacity	Injection Efficiency
Spartan 3E	37,38%	58,19%
Spartan 6	20,87%	54,49%

100 times for the same cipher implementation, clock insertion, and key/IV pair—that is, around 3200 tests. The injection capacity for Spartan 3E is 37.38%, whereas for Spartan 6, it reaches 20.87%. Concerning injection efficiency, it is 58.19% for Spartan 3E and 54.49% for Spartan 6. These results show a lower efficiency when compared with the efficiency obtained for standard implementations. The L.P. Trivium would require to increment the number of injections to retrieve the key with DFA. In any case, it demonstrates that effective fault injection in ciphers is still possible and could be used to obtain secret information.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a vulnerability analysis of the Trivium stream cipher implemented in different FPGA families. Previous theoretical works showed that if an attacker is able to inject a single fault in the internal state of the Trivium, then the attacker would be able to endanger the cryptosystem. A fault injection system is used to introduce faults in four versions of Trivium implemented in two FPGAs families. The maximum frequencies at which the ciphers can operate are very high, introducing a notable difficulty in the physical realization of the fault generation system. A comparison between experimental and simulation results of fault injection is provided. The internal state sampled in the FPGA-based Trivium many cycles after the fault injection occurred has been compared with simulation results of the internal state undergoing the same fault injection at the same cycle. This comparison made sure that the data experimentally measured were correct.

Fault injection results for different pairs key-IV at different clock cycles are reported. It has been possible to inject a single

fault in the internal state for all versions of Trivium. This proves the vulnerability of FPGA-based Trivium implementations to fault attacks. The efficiency of the fault injection system ranges from 68% to 100% for the standard version of Trivium (with parallel or serial load). This efficiency is a bit lower, 58%, for the L.P. version. Our results also show that although the serial-load Trivium with external counter is able to work at higher frequencies, the L.P. version is more resistant to this kind of attack, since the efficiency of the system is lower. On the flip side, the maximum operating frequency of the L.P. Trivium is lower. It can be therefore stated that according to the tests performed and the results obtained, the Trivium implementations on the FPGA are vulnerable to fault injection attack, no matter the kind of implementation targeted and the device to be used for such implementation. It can also be stated that the proposed fault injection system has accomplished very high efficiency.

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